

THE INVADE PROJECT: TOWARDS THE FLEXIBILITY OPERATOR CONCEPT AND ITS APPLICATION TO THE SPANISH PILOT

Pol OLIVELLA-ROSELL
CITCEA-UPC – Spain
pol.olivella@citcea.upc.edu

Pau LLORET-GALLEGO
CITCEA-UPC – Spain
lloret@citcea.upc.edu

Roberto VILLAFILA-ROBLES
CITCEA-UPC - Spain
roberto.villafila@citcea.upc.edu

Stig Ø. OTTESEN
eSmart Systems AS – Norway
stig.ottesen@esmartsystems.com

Ramon GALLART-FERNANDEZ
Estabanell&Pahisa SA – Spain
rgallart@estabanell.cat

Andreas SUMPER
CITCEA-UPC - Spain
sumper@citcea.upc.edu

ABSTRACT

The present work proposes the creation of the Flexibility Operator (FO) role that pools the small flexibilities of customers or network users in order to make use of them in the grid or on energy markets. This FO concept, developed under the INVADE H2020 Project, is then applied to the Spanish pilot case, which offer flexibility services to the DSO and the BRP simultaneously by using a centralized battery installed at the distribution grid.

INTRODUCTION

Past centralized, dispatchable and predictable generation provided flexibility at transmission level to the electric system to balance generation and demand. Now, the increasing number of installed distributed renewable generation is transforming the generation side in a more variable and intermittent source of energy that needs to be managed adequately. In addition, the demand side is becoming more active, which emphasizes the empowerment and engagement of consumers. The proper management of available flexibility, both in generation and demand side, can help to compensate the lack of certainty of renewable sources. Moreover, the new electric loads like electric vehicles and batteries are forcing power systems to evolve.

Several studies and institutions have tried to address this issue and proposed its own methodology and mechanisms to implement flexibility management. The European Commission (EC) has published three mandates to promote Smart Grid standardization process. One of these mandates, the M/490, aims to support European Smart Grid deployment, and under its umbrella, flexibility issues have been addressed at European level to try to standardize its development.

Authors would present the FO concept under development in the INVADE H2020 Project [1]. In this paper, we aim to expose the main characteristics of the FO and the Spanish pilot case study.

THE FLEXIBILITY OPERATOR CONCEPT

According to CEN-CENELEC-ETSI [2], the Flexibility Operator (FO) is a role that pools the small flexibilities of customers or network users in order to make use of

them in the grid or on energy markets. In the same reference, is already mentioned the similarities between FO and aggregator roles. In that sense, and considering the definition of the aggregator from the European Commission [3], the FO does aggregator's tasks.

Figure 1 shows the conceptual model of this flexibility flow. It also defines the FO as a bundled role that pools the small flexibilities of customers or network users in order to make use of them in the grid or on energy markets. Although its name and specific tasks can vary depending on the reference, its main responsibility is to act as an intermediary between a supplier and a user of flexibility.

The FO can offer its flexibility services to energy supplier/BRP, DSO, or final customers. Moreover, the FO role can be played by different current agents like the BRP or remain as a new independent agent. FO portfolio can be composed by different distributed energy resources and they can be organized in local energy communities. Services offered to each of them may be different and can be subject to the following restrictions:

- To offer services to the BRP, the FO must have enough customers in its portfolio that are also customers of this BRP.
- As FO has not the role of a BRP, FO does not participate in the wholesale markets directly. Only under command of the BRP.
- To offer services to the DSO, the FO must have enough customers in its portfolio with grid access to the same part of the grid where the flexibility services are requested.

Additionally, the FO also acts behind the meter, like an energy service company (ESCO). Therefore, during situations without external requests, the FO can operate the flexible resources to minimize the electricity bill of each flexible resource owner.

Thus, the FO can extract the maximum benefits for all from flexible resources depending on each situation.

Figure 1 – Flexibility flow using a centralized operator to link flexibility sources and flexibility customers.

The proposed system approach is the peer-to-platform, which means that the FO acts as a centralized intermediary between a supplier of flexibility and a user of flexibility. It can be done by a completely centralized system with direct controls for all interactions. In that sense, INVADE suggestion is to implement a centralized approach with direct controls for all interactions, especially between DSO/BRP and FO, and FO and flexible resources. It allows more control on actions taken by the customer to deliver its flexibility and it is expected to have less deviations and higher response certainty. Moreover, control decisions are made centrally based on contracts and previously shared information.

THE TRAFFIC LIGHT CONCEPT APPLIED IN INVADE

It is necessary to classify and prioritize sources, services and use cases because a multi-service approach of storage units usage involves high risks and the operational problem could have not a feasible solution.

The traffic light concept (TLC) can help to determine which service has higher priority in each moment, based on the current and forecasted condition of the grid [9], [10]. The TLC defines three different states:

- Green state: it is the “normal operating state”, where the “flexibility market” competitively operates freely. Under this state, the system/grid operator may not request flexibility services and market operation has the highest priority.
- Amber state: it indicates the state where the system/grid operator actively engages with the market in order to prevent the grid system from becoming unstable and entering in the red state. Under this state, the system/grid operator may request flexibility services and grid operation has the highest priority. It is a temporary state until the grid operation becomes safe again.
- Red state: the system/grid operator needs to take control of market interactions in a certain area where a grid constraint has occurred. Under this state, the

grid operator can override contracts existing in the market and execute dedicated emergency actions through flexibility operators in order to re-stabilise the system.

In red and amber states, FO offers its available flexibility to the DSO to solve or avoid problems in the grid, which should only occur in few specific occasions. These services have higher priority than other flexibility requests, and consequently, it is supposed to be highly rewarded. The DSO is responsible for the identification of the grid state and necessities and for the notification of them to the FO. Controlled islanding service at prosumer premises can also be performed in red state. In amber state, surplus flexibility not used to avoid distribution grid problems can be used to satisfy prosumer services if they help the distribution system.

However, in green state flexibility can be offered to the BRP or to prosumers interchangeably. Here, services to the BRP (portfolio optimization for instance) and to the final customer have to compete for the same available flexibility. Before flexibility is offered to other customers in an aggregated way, a prosumer can use its own flexibility for in-home or building optimization. As a first approach, services to the BRP may be less frequent but highly rewarded than the services to the final customer, which are always present by default if no other flexibility request is in place. For that reason, compensation to prosumers for providing flexibility to BRP should exceed the profits they can obtain by the use of its own flexibility for its own benefit.

The TLC system could be useful for the pilots in INVADE, if they see a need for prioritization between flexibility services.

Figure 2 – TLC applied to flexibility services and customers.

FLEXIBILITY SERVICES

Literature has been extensively reviewed for standard definitions on flexibility services. These services are normally classified in function of the flexibility customer, namely, Distribution System Operator (DSO), Balancing Responsible Party (BRP), Transmission System Operator (TSO) and Prosumer; although TSO is out of the scope of the project. By its applicability to the European context, two sources have been identified as key references to define the INVADE services: the

Universal Smart Energy Framework (USEF) [4]–[7] and the conclusions and advices regarding flexibility implementation from the Expert Group 3 (EG3) [8].

Table 1: Flexibility services that can be applied in each TLC state.

Flexibility customer	Flexibility services INVADE	Grid state		
		Green	Amber	Red
DSO	Congestion management		✓	✓
	Voltage/Reactive power control		✓	✓
	Controlled islanding		✓	✓
BRP	Day-ahead portfolio optimization	✓	✓	
	Intraday portfolio optimization	✓	✓	
	Self-balancing portfolio optimization	✓	✓	

DSO and BRP services are not necessarily compatible but the used approach allows to create the mechanism to prioritize them. Table 2 shows seven cases where BRP and DSO requests flexibility. This table applies to amber phases when the DSO needs support and the BRP request could be compatible or not with grid needs. Up-regulation is defined as positive and negative flexibility means down-regulation.

Table 2: BRP and DSO flexibility request compatibility. Flexibility measured in kWh per period

Case	BRP flex. request	DSO flex. request	Flexibility to activate	BRP deviation	DSO deviation
A	100	0	100	0	0
B	0	100	100	0	0
C	100	100	100	0	0
D	200	100	200	0	-100
E	100	200	200	-100	0
F	-100	100	100	-200	0
G	100	-100	-100	200	0

Table 2 shows multiple cases for requested flexibility from the DSO and BRP. Cases A and B are not simultaneous and they can be satisfied by the FO. Case C represents the most beneficial case for the FO as the DSO and BRP will pay for 200 kWh of up-regulation and the FO only has to activate 100 kWh. Cases D and E present two different flexibility requests at the same direction. According the TLC, the FO has to prioritize the DSO needs. In the case D the FO activates 200 kWh because this satisfies the DSO need without causing other problems. In contrast, the FO activates 200 kWh in case E because the DSO request is more restrictive and the BRP has a deviation of 100 kWh. In such situation, as the BRP is getting more flexibility than requested, the FO may not have to pay a deviation penalty to the BRP. Finally, cases F and G show cases with contradictory

requests where the DSO has priority over the BRP needs and the FO has to compensate the BRP to increase its deviation economically. However, the DSO fee to activate flexibility will compensate the BRP deviation penalty.

THE INVADE SPANISH PILOT

The Spanish pilot is based on the use of a centralized battery in a secondary substation to provide services to the local DSO (EPESA) and the BRP/retailer (Mercator). The retailer company, which also is the owner of the installed battery, plays the FO role in this pilot site.

For the DSO, the flexibility will be used to improve the distribution system capacity of integrating renewable and distributed energy. The battery will be used to optimize the use of the flexibility for demand management and power quality improvement and to reduce the medium voltage grid congestions. Additionally, the battery will improve the power quality of supply in the validation area where a critical building is placed, and it will permit to create an electrical island and keep supplying critical loads.

For the BRP, the flexibility will be used to reduce its electricity purchase costs and imbalance penalties. Day-ahead and intraday portfolio optimization aims to shift loads from a high-price time interval to a low-price time interval before day-ahead or intraday markets closure. In contrast, self-balancing optimization aims to reduce imbalances of the BRP within its portfolio to avoid imbalance charges. The BRP does not actively bid on the imbalance market using its load flexibility, but uses it within its own portfolio.

The validation area has 1,625 consumption points, 12 secondary substations and the installed capacity is 7.2 MW. Grid congestion could rise mainly during summer due to air conditioning high consumption. The battery will have 200 kWh of capacity and 200 kW of power. The idea is to first validate the benefits of the use of this battery and then try to extrapolate the results if more batteries are used within the validation area.

The timeline of the actions to plan, execute and settle the use of flexibility are represented in Figure 3. Although in this case a battery is the unique flexible resource used, it also applies to a portfolio of different flexible assets. Scheduling tasks will be executed every 15 minutes, although it can happen days, hours or minutes ahead of the final delivery. The action sequence is as follows:

- The DSO receives grid metered values from its own SCADA system. These values are used as inputs in the grid congestion detection algorithm to quantify the needed flexibility in the forthcoming periods. Then, the DSO sends a flexibility request to the FO if it is needed.
- Similarly, the BRP receives the portfolio forecasts and estimates the future unbalances. If it is needed, it sends a flexibility request to the FO.
- The FO receives all flexibility requests and establishes a prioritization according to the grid status.
- Before scheduling flexibility, the FO checks the

available amount of flexibility from the battery.

- Then, it produces the flexibility plan containing all management signals to be sent later on.

Once the flexibility plan has been applied, the settlement process audits what happened during every period. The settlement process is as follows:

- The FO platform receives metered values from the used battery.
- The FO calculates the activated flexibility during the settlement previous period of operation.
- The FO settles the BRP, the DSO and the battery according to their flexibility contracts.
- The FO sends delivery notes and bills to the BRP and the DSO for the activated flexibility service.

Figure 3: Flexibility operation and settlement timeline.

If external flexibility sources are used, they also need to be paid for their activated flexibility. In this case, as the FO owns the battery, it is not needed to deliver notes and bills to the activated flexibility source owner.

CONCLUSIONS

The present work presented the role of the Flexibility Operator (FO) providing services to the DSO and BRP simultaneously. The Traffic Light Concept (TLC) allows the FO to clearly prioritize the flexibility requests. The Spanish pilot case will allow to develop a new technical solution and to test the economic feasibility of these concepts. In addition, this project will offer the opportunity to explore the role of the FO and learn about the new business opportunities it offers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has been supported by INVADE H2020 project (2017-2019), which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 731148.

REFERENCES

- [1] "INVADE H2020 Project Grant Agreement 731148," 2017. [Online]. Available: www.h2020invade.eu. [Accessed: 20-Oct-2017]
- [2] E. Joint Working Group on Standards for Smart Grids (CENELEC, CEN, *SG-CG / M490 / L Flexibility Management - Flexibility Management Overview of the main concepts of flexibility management*. Smart Grid Coordination Group, 2014.
- [3] European Commission, "DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on common rules for the internal market in electricity," *Eur. Comm. Winter Packag.*, 2016.
- [4] M. van den Berge, M. Broekmans, B. Derksen, A. Papanikolaou, and C. Malavazos, "Flexibility provision in the Smart Grid era using USEF and OS4ES," in *2016 IEEE International Energy Conference (ENERGYCON)*, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [5] Smart Energy Collective, "An introduction to the Universal Smart Energy Framework," 2013 [Online]. Available: www.smartenergycollective.com
- [6] USEF Foundation, "USEF: The Framework Specifications," 2015 [Online]. Available: www.usef.energy/download-the-framework
- [7] USEF Foundation, "USEF: The framework explained," 2015 [Online]. Available: www.usef.energy/download-the-framework/
- [8] M. Sánchez-Jiménez, K. Stamatis, M. Kollau, M. Stantcheva, E. Busechian, P. Hermans, D. Guzeleva, G. E. Abrandt, W. Friedl, P. Mandatova, and J. Stromback, *Regulatory Recommendations for the Deployment of Flexibility*. Smart Grid Task Force - Expert Group 3: Regulatory Recommendations for Smart Grids Deployment, 2015 [Online]. Available: [http://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/EG3 Final - January 2015.pdf](http://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/EG3_Final_-_January_2015.pdf)
- [9] German Association of the Energy and Water Industry (BDEW), "Smart Grid Traffic Light Concept. Design of the amber phase. Discussion paper.," 2015.
- [10] Bundesverband der Energie und Wasserwirtschaft (BDEW), "Elements of a dynamically developing internal market for electricity and gas," 2014.